

Supporting information

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1. Proposed mechanism of the anomalous current

The anomalous current may be the persistent photocurrent (PPC), the persistence of the photocurrent after the termination of photoexcitation. The impurity levels introduced by dopants Fe and Co act as trap states or recombination centers. Photoexcited free electrons or holes captured by these deep or shallow traps normally cause PPC. In contrast to the band-to-band recombination, PPC extends the decay time because free electrons or holes are re-trapped before recombination.

2. Discontinuation of the present study

While the proposed mechanism of PPC provides a potential explanation, experimental validation is incomplete. Due to adverse circumstances in the research environment, I have withdrawn from my studies and was therefore unable to obtain further experimental results to complete a comprehensive scientific discussion.